

Konzorcij projektnih pisarn za krepitev odličnosti, interdisciplinarnosti
in mednarodne vpetosti slovenskega raziskovalnega prostora

NATIONAL INSTITUTE
OF CHEMISTRY

HANDBOOK

**Project Management
in EU Grant Funding**

HANDBOOK

**Project Management
in EU Grant Funding**

HANDBOOK, Project Management in EU Grant Funding, National Institute of Chemistry

Authors: dr. Barbara Tišler, Ivica Ilić, Nastja Vodeb, Ana Železnik, Tina Letić

Editor: Nastja Vodeb

Design: Jure Legac

Published and issued by: National Institute of Chemistry, Hajdrihova 19, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenija

Complimentary publication

For publisher: prof. dr. Gregor Anderluh

Year of Publication: 2024

Printed by: Demago d.o.o., Maribor

Circulation: 300 issues

Table of Contents:

INTRODUCTION TO PROJECT MANAGEMENT	6
INTRODUCTION TO HORIZON EUROPE	12
RELEVANT CONTACT POINTS AT THE NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF CHEMISTRY	17
NAVIGATING EU FUNDING AND TENDERS PORTAL	21
GRANT AGREEMENT PREPARATION PROCEDURE	28
GRANT AGREEMENT AND DESCRIPTION OF ACTION (DoA)	32
REPORTING UNDER HORIZON EUROPE	36
COMMUNICATION	40
DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION	45
HELPFUL GUIDELINES	49
TEMPLATES	50

Table of Figures:

FIGURE 1.1. PDCA cycle	7
FIGURE 1.2. Project life cycle	8
FIGURE 2.1. Horizon Europe pillars	13
FIGURE 3.1. Project application flowchart	18
FIGURE 3.2. PMO team	19
FIGURE 4.1. Funding & Tenders portal	21
FIGURE 4.2. Find Funding & Tenders opportunities	22
FIGURE 4.3. Use filters to find opportunities	22
FIGURE 4.4. Detailed information about the opportunity and opening a new submission form	23
FIGURE 4.5. Completing the proposal form	23
FIGURE 4.6. Continuous reporting	25
FIGURE 4.7. Participants search tool	26
FIGURE 4.8. Information and resources	27

Guidelines:

FIGURE 10.1. EU Funding and Tenders Online Manual	49
FIGURE 10.2. National Contact points for Horizon Europe	49
FIGURE 10.3. Horizon Europe Programme Guide	49
FIGURE 10.4. EU Grants Amendment Guide	49
FIGURE 10.5. Common mistakes to avoid	49
FIGURE 10.6. CORDIS - database of projects supported by HE	49
FIGURE 10.7. EU guidelines on the responsible use of generative AI in research	49
FIGURE 10.8. European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity	49
FIGURE 10.9. European Commission's Research and Innovation Portal	49
FIGURE 10.10. European IP Helpdesk	50
FIGURE 10.11. Gender in EU research	50
FIGURE 10.12. Horizon Results Booster	50
FIGURE 10.13. Horizon Europe Results Platform	50

FIGURE 10.14. Partnering opportunities – Enterprise Europe Network	50
FIGURE 10.15. Partnering opportunities – Funding and Tenders Portal	50

Templates:

FIGURE 11.1. Minutes of the meeting	50
FIGURE 11.2. Periodic report	50
FIGURE 11.3. Horizon Europe Reference documents	50

Tables:

TABLE 1.1. Project features	9
TABLE 1.2. Project management terms	9
TABLE 5.1. The difference between Grant agreement and Consortium agreement	28
TABLE 5.2. Roles of beneficiary as project partner	28
TABLE 5.3. Roles of beneficiary as project coordinator	30
TABLE 6.1. Grant agreement amendments	35
TABLE 7.1. Reporting responsibilities based on beneficiary's role	36
TABLE 7.2. Mandatory reporting based on types of action	37
TABLE 7.3. Types of reporting	39
TABLE 8.1. Beneficiary's roles based on type of communication	42
TABLE 9.1. Dissemination tools based on stakeholders	46
TABLE 9.2. Use of CDE Plan in different stages of the project	48

1. INTRODUCTION TO PROJECT MANAGEMENT

6

After the information revolution and software development at the beginning of the millennium, the **project management approach** slowly began to establish itself as an effective approach and the dominant method for project implementation. The approach allows greater orientation towards goals, greater motivation of all parties involved, better relations with partners and easier control and monitoring of a project. **Project management methodology** is a system of principles, techniques and procedures used by project managers. In modern times it has begun to establish itself as a profession in a wider spectrum of business sectors. It brings the most effective set of tools of modern times as its very essence is the creation of new value for the organization (for example: increasing cash flow, creating social value, creating a brand). Project management methods and tools are constantly evolving, new ideas and more modern and efficient approaches are being developed to manage the time and costs of implementation while controlling the quality of the results created. Not only do top methodologies differ in how they are structurally organized, but they also require different deliverables and workflows. Project management in **grant funding** involves overseeing the planning, execution, and monitoring of research or innovation projects funded by the European Commission (hereinafter EC). This process ensures that the objectives outlined in the grant proposal are achieved efficiently and effectively. It includes tasks such as budget management, team coordination, reporting progress to the commission, and adhering to project timelines. Effective project management is crucial for maximizing the impact of funded projects and ensuring they contribute to the advancement of science and technology in Europe. In order to facilitate the management of projects at the EU level, the EC has developed the so-called **PM² Guide 3.0.1**, methodology that aims to ensure open access to all member states of EU. It enables project teams to manage their projects effectively, and to deliver solutions and benefits to their organizations and stakeholders. It is completely free to use and all related materials (methodological guide, project templates, training material) are available for each project team to adapt to their needs. PM² has been successfully used across the EU in various projects and enables greater efficiency in the management and communication of project work that serves the objectives of the EU and the needs of Member States and EU citizens. While the methodology is suitable to any type of project, it is ideal for projects related to the public sector, EU programmes and grants.

Project is a time-limited undertaking of a temporary nature, which has a specific beginning and end, and its essence is the creation of unique results and services.

The end of a project is: (1) when the goal is achieved, or (2) when the goal is terminated (the goal cannot be achieved, the need no longer exists, or the project funder wants it to end). From the point of view of the process, the project is a one-time, goal-oriented complex process that has time, resources and financial constraints. It consists of logically linked set of autonomous, yet interdependent activities, and its purpose is to create a unique result. It can also be said that the project is coordination of the implementation of related activities through a final,

goal-oriented, unique process. The goal of the project is the team creation of the planned results, considering the planned quality, planned time and estimated costs. A project can have various impacts, from social, economic or environmental, and they are characterized by going beyond the project. Some of the world-renowned phenomena created by the project approach are a good indicator of good project management practice. These include, for example, designing the pyramids, the Olympic Games, the development of computer applications, the development of vaccines, and the positioning of the International Space Station in Earth's orbit. Various forms of optimization, transformation or digitization of business processes can also be counted among the projects, and the project approach is also useful in the field of planning the reconstruction of social infrastructure.

The Circle of Logic, also known as the **Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA)** is a fundamental concept that guides how projects are planned, executed, and improved over time. PDCA is a continuous process of planning, doing, checking, and acting, helping you manage your project effectively from start to finish. Imagine it as a continuous loop that helps you navigate through your project effectively. Here's how it works (**Figure 1.1.**).

FIGURE 1.1.
PDCA

On the other hand, the project life cycle is a broad set of guidelines for approaching new projects. The project life cycle is actually a timeline and plan of the project management process from start to finish, where each project should have unique and well-thought-out objectives for each phase. Once these goals are achieved, a new phase can begin. All projects, regardless of their size and complexity, generally follow the same life cycle structure, as we can see in **Figure 1.2**. It consists of (1) initiation, (2) planning, (3) implementation and (4) closing phases.

8 In the initiation phase, decision-making activities are carried out on whether the organization will even invest the resources needed for the next phase, while in the next, planning phase, a detailed plan for the implementation of the project is prepared and made. In the implementation phase, the project is physically implemented, all activities for the implementation of the project are carried out. In the closing phase, individual activities are carried out, which complete the project. It is necessary to monitor and control the project throughout all phases of the life cycle as projected in the picture above.

FIGURE 1.2.
Project life cycle

By its very nature, project work is the opposite of classic regular work, where it mostly involves standardized, repetitive processes. The **general features of the project** are further defined in the **Table 1.1**. below. The goal of classic approaches to work is to maintain the continuity of the business, while the essence of the project approach is primarily the realization of the project's goal and its completion.

TABLE 1.1.
Project features

Uniqueness and Singularity	We create unique results with the project. It is unlikely that the project will be repeated in the same way or with the same participants.
Temporarity	Projects are time-limited with clearly agreed time limits, the start and the end.
Goal orientation	All project activities are planned and executed in such a way that the set goals are achieved.
Limitation	Every project has constraints, the most common of which are quality, deadline, and budget available for project implementation.
Co-creation and Complexity	The project can include very complex and interwoven and a wide range of people with different jurisdictions and responsibilities, therefore particularly careful coordination and control of the implementation, costs and deadlines within the project is required.
Co-Dependence	The implementation of the project depends on the implementation of interdependent activities, which are characterized by the fact that one activity cannot be started before the previous activity is finished, and vice versa.
Riskiness	In contrast to regular work, where everything is done according to established procedures with proven solutions, the project is associated with conflictness and uniqueness. The project manager may be surprised by many things during the implementation of the project, such as implementation problems, realization of risks, influential individuals, environmental changes, etc.

The uniqueness of the project is expressed through the creation of a new, unrepeatable result. With the next project, the conditions, environment, participants, and the rest will definitely change. One of the basic and fundamental characteristics is its temporary nature, which means that the project has a precisely defined beginning and end. This, on the other hand, does not apply to the results that the project creates, as these are usually permanent, unlike the implementation of the project. Limitation is also one of the features of every project, as the project manager must anticipate and coordinate all of the competing constraints in order to successfully implement the project. Besides project features, you can find some of the most basic project management terms in the **Table 1.2.** below.

TABLE 1.2.
Project management terms

Call for proposal	The process by which EU invites potential suppliers to submit proposals for the execution of a contract, aka funding of a project.
Consortium	Group formed to undertake an enterprise beyond the resources of any one member, that work together to achieving a common objective.
Kickoff meeting	The first meeting between a project team and stakeholders. It serves to review project expectations and to build enthusiasm for a project.

Gantt chart	A project management tool that illustrates work completed over a period of time in relation to the time planned for the work. Tasks and activities are listed vertically, with the horizontal axis marking time. The lengths of task bars are to scale with tasks' durations. It offers a microscopic view of every detail of your project like current task progress, task priorities, milestones, deliverables, time estimates, etc.
WP	Work package is a group of related tasks and activities within a project. Because they look like projects themselves, they are often thought of as sub-projects within a larger project.
Task	The smallest unit of work necessary to complete a project work package.
Subtask	The first meeting between a project team and stakeholders. It serves to review project expectations and to build enthusiasm for a project.
KPI	A Key performance indicator is a metric for measuring project success. They are established before project execution begins.
Input	The information required to start the project management process.
Output	The final measurable result received upon successful completion of a project when all planned tasks and activities are accomplished and project deliverables are produced.
Deliverables	A report that is sent to the granting authority, providing information to ensure effective monitoring of the project. There are different types of deliverables (e.g. a report on specific activities or results, data management plans, ethics or security requirements). Those are the outputs to be submitted to the EU (publication, leaflet, progress report, brochure, list, etc.)
Milestones	Control points in the project that help to chart progress (kick-off meetings, steering committees, first-draft of a survey, prototype, etc.). Milestones may correspond to the achievement of a key result, allowing the next phase of the work to begin. They may also be needed at intermediary points so that, if problems have arisen, corrective measures can be taken. A milestone may be a critical decision point in the project where, for example, the consortium must decide which of several technologies to adopt for further development.
TRL	Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is the concept of evaluating the innovation maturity of the project, product, technology. It is used by the EC under Horizon Europe program, to define the level of development of certain projects.

Typical project participants are individuals or organizations that actively participate in the project in at least one of the project phases. Some of the most typical project participants are project funder, project coordinator, project manager project partner, project team and **project management office**.

Project funder is usually a legal entity acting as a project investor. The EU provides funding for a range of projects and programmes. Through Grant Agreement, it applies strict rules, for tight control over how funds are used and to ensure money is spent in a transparent, accountable manner. Management of EU funding: (1) centralized management: EU funding is managed directly by the EC, (2) decentralised management: the EC and national authorities jointly manage the funding, (3) indirect management: funding is managed by partner organizations or other authorities inside or outside the EU.

Project coordinator is a leading organization and the first point of contact on behalf of consortium who receives funding directly from the grant and is responsible to distribute resources among partners. Its primary responsibility is to initiate and manage the grant and consortium agreements. This involves identifying consortium partners and establishing collaboration among them, defining roles, and ensuring a clear understanding of project objectives and timelines. The coordinator oversees the creation and submission of the grant proposal for evaluation. Once approved, they draft, coordinate and finalise the consortium agreement – a legally binding contract outlining cooperation terms and resource sharing among partners. In the implementation phase, he manages the distribution of payments received from the EC to consortium partners, ensuring transparent financial transactions in compliance with the grant agreement. Additionally, they strategically plan and allocate project resources for maximum impact on project success.

Principal Investigator (hereinafter: PI) is responsible for the preparation, conduct, and administration of a research grant, cooperative agreement, training or public service project, contract, or other sponsored project. Responsibilities include: takes overall responsibility for the project's success and outcomes, develops the research proposal or project plan, secures funding for the project, leads the research team and ensures compliance with regulations, often has expertise in the project's subject matter.

Project manager is an operational body to which the leading organization assigns, commits or assigns responsibility for achieving project goals and is fully responsible for the planning and execution of a specific project. He should be a comprehensive personality with appropriate personality traits and a wide range of knowledge, competences, skills and experience, as he is expected to be able to assemble the tasks of experts in a wide variety of fields into a connected, coordinated and functioning whole. At the same time, he is the bearer of the most vital project function and is operationally responsible for the implementation of the entire project. Usually, this is the person who creates good business and personal relationships in the project team among members who do not know each other. The appointment of a project manager must therefore be planned and prudent, since such a choice implies his direct responsibility for the representation and implementation of the project. Responsibilities include (but not limited to): assists in creating project plans and schedules, coordinates and schedules meetings and workshops, maintains project documentation and records, communicates with team members to ensure tasks are completed on time, helps track project expenses and budget adherence, assists in identifying and managing risks.

Project partner is any organization who will not receive funding directly from the grant, but is a participant on equal basis who has an integral role in the proposed research due to their expertise, experience, and reputation in the relevant project domain and industry.

Project team is a multidisciplinary group of different experts, who are selected according to the requirements and needs of the project and participate in the implementation of the

project with their professional knowledge and experience. Members of the project team have precisely defined tasks among themselves, for the execution of which cooperation and teamwork are crucial.

12

Project Management Office (hereinafter: PMO) is an organizational unit in which all resources for successful project management are concentrated. The goal of the PMO is to monitor the available capacities of the organization, while at the same time taking care of their proper use over a long period of time, in order to ensure the highest possible level of efficiency of project implementation. Their duties are of a more administrative nature and include support, such as conducting trainings for researchers, announcing opportunities and presenting current national and international calls for proposals, finding suitable partners at brokerage events, integrated administration of coordinating projects, consulting in writing project proposals and full support until Grant Agreement signature.

2. INTRODUCTION TO HORIZON EUROPE

Horizon Europe is the European Union's **framework programme for research and innovation (R&I)** for 2021-2027. Horizon Europe is the EU's key funding programme for research and innovation with a budget of €95.5 billion.

The aim of the programme is to strengthen the EU's scientific and technological basis, including by developing solutions to address policy priorities like the green and digital transitions. The programme also contributes to achieving sustainable development goals and boosts competitiveness and growth. It is the EU's leading initiative to support R&I from concept to market. It tackles climate change, helps to achieve the UN's Sustainable Development Goals and boosts the EU's competitiveness and growth.

The programme facilitates collaboration and strengthens the impact of research and innovation in developing, supporting and implementing EU policies while tackling global challenges. It supports creating and better dispersing of excellent knowledge and technologies. Legal entities from the EU and associated countries can participate.

Europe's future growth and prosperity depend on its ability to remain a **world leader in research and innovation**. Horizon Europe provides the means needed to reach this goal. As such, Horizon Europe ensures that the EU's work in the areas of science and technology has an impact in terms of tackling major global challenges in critical areas such as **health, ageing, security, pollution and climate change**.

It creates jobs, fully engages the EU's talent pool, boosts economic growth, promotes industrial competitiveness and optimises investment impact within a strengthened (hereinafter ERA). The programme is expected to create **up to 100 000 jobs** in R&I activities between 2021 and 2027. It is also projected to increase the EU's gross domestic product (GDP) by **up to 0.19 % over 25 years**.

FIGURE 2.1.
Horizon Europe pillars

(source: Horizon Europe Programme Guide)

Horizon Europe is made up of **three pillars**:

1. Excellent science,
2. global challenges and European industrial competitiveness,
3. innovative Europe.

An additional part underpinning the entire programme supports the extension of excellence-based participation from all member states. This will serve to optimise national research and innovation potential across Europe, and thereby strengthen the **European Research Area**.

The first Horizon Europe pillar reinforces the **EU's scientific leadership**, promoting the development of high-quality knowledge and skills. It supports frontier research projects through the European Research Council and boosts investment in research infrastructures. **The Excellent Science Pillar** aims to increase the EU's global scientific competitiveness. It supports frontier research projects driven by top researchers through the European Research Council, funds fellowships for experienced researchers, doctoral training networks and exchanges through Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions, and invests in world-class research infrastructures. The Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions fund researchers' mobility, training and career development activities.

The second pillar supports research and innovation that addresses societal challenges and industrial technologies in areas such as **health, digital, climate, energy, mobility, civil security, food and natural resources**. **The Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness Pillar** supports research relating to societal challenges and reinforces tech-

nological and industrial capacities through clusters. It sets ambitious goals for EU missions. It also includes the Joint Research Centre which supports EU and national policymakers with independent scientific evidence and technical support.

14

Horizon Europe introduces research and innovation **missions**, such as on climate-neutral and smart cities, as well as European **partnerships**, for example on clean hydrogen. This pillar also includes activities pursued by the Joint Research Centre (JRC).

The third Horizon Europe pillar focuses on promoting all forms of innovation, and in particular breakthrough and disruptive innovation, through the **European Innovation Council (Hereandafter EIC)**. The EIC offers a one-stop-shop for innovators with high potential to create markets for the future. **The Innovative Europe Pillar** aims to make Europe a frontrunner in market-creating innovation via the EIC. It also helps to develop the overall EU innovation landscape through the European Institute of Innovation and Technology which fosters integration of the knowledge triangle of education, research and innovation.

Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area (Hereandafter ERA) by increasing support to the EU Member States in their efforts to make the most of their national research and innovation potential, fostering closer collaborations and spreading excellence.

New elements in Horizon Europe

- **EIC:** Support for innovations with potential breakthrough and disruptive nature with scale-up potential that may be too risky for private investors. This is 70% of the budget earmarked for SMEs.
- **Missions:** Sets of measures to achieve bold, inspirational and measurable goals within a set timeframe. There are 5 main mission areas as part of Horizon Europe.
- **Open science policy:** Mandatory open access to publications and open science principles are applied throughout the programme Factsheet: Open science in Horizon Europe
- **New approach to partnerships:** Objective-driven and more ambitious partnerships with industry in support of EU policy objectives

EIC has been established under the EU **Horizon Europe** programme. It has a budget of €10.1 billion to support game changing innovations throughout the lifecycle from early stage research, to proof of concept, technology transfer, and the financing and scale up of start-ups and SMEs.

The strategy and implementation of the EIC is steered by the **EIC Board**, which has independent members appointed from the world of innovation (entrepreneurs, researchers, investors, corporates and others from the innovation ecosystem).

The **EIC and SME Executive Agency** responsible for supporting the EIC Board and its President, and for implementing the EIC's activities which are set out in an annual **EIC Work Programme**. The funding and support available in 2024 is organised into three main funding schemes: the EIC Pathfinder for advanced research to develop the scientific basis to underpin breakthrough technologies (Section II); the EIC Transition to validate technologies and develop business plans for specific applications (Section III); and the EIC Accelerator to support companies (SMEs, start-ups, spin-offs and in exceptional cases small mid-caps) to bring their innovations to market and scale them up (Section IV). In each case, the direct financial support to innovators is augmented with access to a range of Business Acceleration Services (Section V) providing access to leading expertise, corporates, investors and ecosystem actors. All of the main calls (Pathfinder, Transition, Accelerator) provide for *Open* funding which can support technologies and innovations in any field without any predefined priority areas. In the case of the Pathfinder and Accelerator, this Open funding is complemented by a set of *Challenges* which target specific technologies and innovations of strategic interest for the Union, including to support initiatives such as Net Zero Industry, Critical Raw Materials, the Chips Act, and Health Emergency Responses. Outside of the calls, a budget is also set aside to support follow on investments to companies selected under previous EIC Work Programmes.

EU Missions are a new way to bring concrete solutions to some of our greatest challenges. They have ambitious goals and will deliver concrete results by 2030.

The 5 EU Missions are:

1. Adaptation to Climate Change: support at least 150 European regions and communities to become climate resilient by 2030,
2. Cancer: working with Europe's Beating Cancer Plan to improve the lives of more than 3 million people by 2030 through prevention, cure and solutions to live longer and better,
3. Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030,
4. 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030,
5. A Soil Deal for Europe: 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030.

EU Missions are a novelty of the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme for the years 2021-2027. They put research and innovation into a new role, combined with new forms of governance and collaboration, as well as by engaging citizens.

They support Commission priorities, such as the European Green Deal, Europe fit for the Digital Age, Beating Cancer and the New European Bauhaus. For instance, Mission Climate is a concrete element of the new Climate Adaptation Strategy, Mission Cancer of the Europe's Beating Cancer Plan and the Mission Soil is a flagship initiative of the Long-term Vision for the EU's Rural Areas.

EU Missions are a coordinated effort by the Commission to pool the necessary resources in terms of policies and regulations, as well as other activities. They also aim to mobilise and activate public and private actors, such as EU Member States, regional and local authorities, research institutes, farmers and land managers, entrepreneurs and investors to create real and lasting impact. Missions engage with citizens to boost societal uptake of new solutions and approaches.

16

EU Missions support Europe's transformation into a greener, healthier, more inclusive and resilient continent. They aim to bring tangible benefits to people in Europe and engage Europeans in their design, implementation and monitoring.

Open science: Support and reward a true open science culture across the Union, including mainstreaming open access to scholarly publications and research data (*i.e.* following the "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" principle) and the diffusion and uptake of open science principles and practices, whilst considering differences between disciplines and cultural differences, including multilingualism, supporting the development of open science skills, and further developing and integrating the underpinning digital infrastructure and services.

A quarter of the funds in Horizon Europe go to partnerships, formerly known as Joint Undertakings. Through the partnerships, the European Commission enters into agreements whereby funds from the framework programmes will be used together with funds from member states or from the business sector. The bulk of the funds go to industry-oriented partnerships.

There are three types of partnerships: co-financed, agreement-based, and institutional. Calls for proposals from the partnerships represent great opportunities for Norwegian research groups and companies.

3. RELEVANT CONTACT POINTS AT THE NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF CHEMISTRY

It is important to understand who are the relevant contact people at the Institute who are involved in the project preparation and implementation from idea to final report, when is funded by the European Commission funds through predefined funding instruments.

Namely, there are three offices that support you in your funding journey:

17

- At the time of project preparation, the most relevant contact is the Project Management Office (hereinafter PMO). Head of the PMO is Mr. Ivica Ilić, who is in charge of coordinating support for the preparation of the project proposal, until the submission. In case of successful proposal, support is extended until the signature of the Grant Agreement (see Section 5 for details).
- At the time of project there are two offices: Office for monitoring of international projects (for Horizon, LIFE, etc) – led by Mrs. Maruša Rajovec and Plans and Analysis (for INTERREG, ERA.Net, etc) – led by Mrs. Urša Korošec. These offices help in making plans for expenditures, coordinate the preparation of the financial reports and advice on maximum budget spending.

3.1 Project management office (PMO)

PMO has been operating at the National Institute of Chemistry since 2016, currently as part of the Department for Development and Quality of the National Institute of Chemistry. In addition to the manager, 4 project coordinators are employed in the office. Our PMO is also coordinating 5xPRO project for strengthening excellence, interdisciplinarity and international involvement of the Slovenian research area. The goal of the project is to increase knowledge and competences among support staff and to improve collaboration between the project associates in the 5xPRO Consortium, including NGOs, researchers and key stakeholders. Total value of the project: €1,249,965.09, and it is co-financed by the Republic of Slovenia, the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation and the European Union - Next-GenerationEU.

The key task of our PMO is to support researchers in applying for international projects. The latter mainly include calls for proposals of the Framework Program for Science and Innovation of the European Union, Interreg, Life+, EIT KIC, UN and American calls for proposals and all other calls for proposals that require an international consortium when applying (WEAVE, M. Era - Net, NKFIH, FWO, FWF). In recent years, the number of submitted projects has been around **100 applications per year, the success rate is above the European average, namely around 16% on average. In 2022, the success rate was 25%, which is better than the average (13.95%) for Slovenia and (15.9%) for the EU.** A comparative analysis of public research organizations on the topic of obtaining grants from the Horizon Europe program places the National Institute of Chemistry in second place, right after the University of Ljubljana. The

average amount of grants per project in the Horizon Europe program (total amount of funds obtained / number of approved projects) ranks the National Institute of Chemistry in first place in Slovenia with an average of EUR 677,221.70, far above other research organizations (the next organization has an average of EUR 374,105.19).

New Regulation (Article 64 of ZZRID) & PMO Role

18

In late 2023, a new rulebook (Rulebook on special national projects and salary determination for researchers) was issued, mandating research organizations to establish remuneration calculation procedures.

At NIC, a forthcoming internal rulebook will introduce **an expanded role for PMO staff**. They'll be tasked with **budget calculations based on actual costs and lump sum**, per the new rulebook.

To facilitate this, PMO staff will require detailed project, team, and scope information, structured in a **questionnaire**. Team leaders must submit a fully completed questionnaire to the PMO **14 days before the proposal deadline**. Late submissions may receive limited PMO support.

Note: The questionnaire is mandatory for all researchers submitting proposals with the Institute's PIC code, even after the deadline.

FIGURE 3.1.
Project application flowchart

Support to researchers is provided through regular information, presentation of possibilities for international applications, as well as through personal contacts with individual researchers. The goal of PMO is also the integration of the researchers of the National Institute of Chemistry into international networks (SusChem, EARTO, EERA, IM4Europe, Processes4Planet) and enabling cooperation with decision-makers in the field of scientific policy at the EU level. When writing project proposals, we provide support for international project applications. Support

in filling out the application form includes content development with author's texts, support in administration, communication with partners and preparation of financial structures. PMO is focused exclusively on project applications, until the moment of signing the co-financing agreement (Grant Agreement) and the signing of the consortium agreement.

Timing is the key to the successful execution of the calls for proposals documentation. Work processes for each project must be planned, organized and managed. That's why administration is the biggest share of the tasks to be completed by our PMO. This allows researcher to focus on the project application only, butting away the administrative issues and extensive communication related to that. This includes handling the Funding and Tenders portal, collection and administration of project information related to the online content to be added in the proposal, preparation of templates and guidance for the application form and budgeting, communication with partners in terms of budget justification and issues related to the portal, as well as completion of key parts in the proposal related to ethics, security, summary, and so on.

We also prepare a timetable for each application, which we share with the researcher-applicant and with all consortium partners. The initial outlines of the work plan of the project application also divide the roles in the project and the tasks that each partner must complete by a certain deadline. This is made in the form of a table. Those selected to lead certain work groups are explained why they were chosen and what their responsibilities are.

The ethics of good and fair cooperation is the basis of the work of our PMO. A successful project requires an open exchange of opinions during the preparation of the project documentation. Therefore, the project application process begins with a conversation with the applicant, during which the project topic is illuminated from different angles.

Project application deadlines are regularly communicated with researchers and department heads. Keep in mind that the role of the researcher (coordinator or partner), requires different tasks for the researcher him/herself and the PMO. These tasks take time, so it is extremely important for the researcher to approach the office in due time, so we are able to manage all tasks and assignments in due time, and due quality.

Key contacts

General email of the PMO:

project.office@ki.si / projektna.pisarna@ki.si

Head of the PMO: ivica.ilic@ki.si

Project coordinators:

nastja.vodeb@ki.si | nina.carman@ki.si,
ana.zeleznik@ki.si | tina.letic@ki.si.

FIGURE 3.2.

PMO team

3.2. Office for monitoring of international projects & Plans and Analysis:

20

The mission of the offices is to support researcher in financial planning and implementation. Their principle is the maximum budget spending, according to the plan, taking into account foreseen resources planned during the project preparation. On a daily basis, their care is to calculate all the costs related to the project. In order to do so, it is of extreme importance to have well-structured and balanced budget, open communication and prompt information about the potential changes.

Before the start of the project implementation, offices are organising joint event with the Principal Investigator, researcher from the institute. This is official transfer of the project from the PMO to the implementation part. Goal of the meeting is to go through the structure of the budget, point out major purchases, naming the people that will be involved in the project (existing employees), potential new employments. Documents needed for the meeting are: Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement, Application form and detailed budget breakdown. Based on the documents and meeting outcomes, offices are preparing long-term plan of expenditures and agree with the researcher. This is then implementing and revising each year.

Key contacts

- **Head of the Office for monitoring of international projects:**
marusa.rajovec@ki.si
- **Head of the Plans and Analysis office:**
ursa.korosec@ki.si

4. NAVIGATING EU FUNDING AND TENDERS PORTAL

Funding & Tenders Portal is the official online platform of the EC for accessing information, submitting proposals, and managing projects related to EU funding programs, including Horizon Europe. It serves as a central hub for researchers, innovators, businesses, public authorities, and other stakeholders to engage with EU funding opportunities and initiatives. It is a user-friendly platform for accessing, applying for, and managing EU funding opportunities, supporting the EC efforts to promote research, innovation, and collaboration. Key features and functions of the Funding & Tenders Portal include:

21

Accessing the Portal:

- Visit the Funding and Tenders Portal website:
<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home>
- You will need an EU Login account to access the portal.

FIGURE 4.1.

Funding and Tenders Portal

Funding Opportunities: The portal provides comprehensive information on EU funding programs, calls for proposals, and funding opportunities across various thematic areas, including research, innovation, education, and infrastructure.

- Once logged in, you can browse funding opportunities under “Funding & Tenders Opportunities.”
- Use the search filters to narrow down opportunities by program, topic, deadline, etc.
- Click on an opportunity to view detailed information, including the call text, eligibility criteria, and submission instructions.

FIGURE 4.2.
Find Funding & Tenders opportunities

22

FIGURE 4.3.
Use filters to find opportunities

FIGURE 4.4.

Detailed information about the opportunity and opening a new submission form

23

Submission Process: Researchers, organizations, and consortia can use the portal to submit proposals for EU-funded projects. This includes preparing and submitting project proposals, budgets, work plans, and other required documentation.

- To submit a proposal for funding, navigate to the relevant call and click on "Submit Proposal."
- Follow the instructions to complete the proposal form, including uploading required documents such as the project description, budget, and consortium details.
- Submit the proposal before the deadline.

REMEMBER: Participant Identification Code (PIC) for the National Institute of Chemistry is **998756718!**

FIGURE 4.5.

Completing the proposal form

Evaluation and Selection:

- After the submission deadline, proposals undergo evaluation by independent experts according to predefined criteria.
- Successful proposals are selected for funding based on evaluation results and available budget.

24

Grant Agreement Preparation (Hereandafter GAP) session:

- If your proposal is selected for funding, you will enter into negotiations with the European Commission to finalize the terms of the grant agreement.
- This process involves clarifying project details, budget allocations, and reporting requirements.

Project Implementation: Once awarded funding, project coordinators and partners can use the portal to manage project activities, budgets, reporting obligations, and communication with the European Commission and other stakeholders.

- Once the grant agreement is signed, you can begin implementing your project according to the agreed-upon work plan and budget.
- Adhere to reporting requirements, financial rules, and project milestones throughout the implementation phase.

Reporting and Monitoring:

- Regularly submit the continuous reporting through the Participant Portal.
- Comply with monitoring visits and audits conducted by the European Commission or designated agencies.

FIGURE 4.6.
Continuous reporting

25

(source: EC)

Project Closure:

- At the end of the project, submit a final report and financial statement summarizing project outcomes, achievements, and expenditure.
- Ensure all project-related documents are properly archived and accessible for auditing purposes.

Additional Resources: The portal offers access to guidance documents, manuals, templates, and other resources to assist applicants and beneficiaries in navigating EU funding programs, proposal preparation, project implementation, and reporting.

- Explore the Funding and Tenders Portal's Help section for guides, FAQs, and video tutorials on using the platform.
- Contact the European Commission's Research Enquiry Service for specific inquiries or assistance with Horizon Europe funding opportunities.

26

Participant Search: The portal features a participant search tool, allowing users to find potential project partners, collaborators, and experts across Europe and beyond. This facilitates networking and collaboration in the context of EU-funded projects. You can find it in the menu "Funding", by selecting the option "Participant Register", and clicking the option "Search PIC". If you need partners, there is always an option "Partner Search" in the same menu.

FIGURE 4.7.
Participants search tool

Information and Resources: The portal offers access to guidance documents, manuals, templates, and other resources to assist applicants and beneficiaries in navigating EU funding programs, proposal preparation, project implementation, and reporting. You can find it in the menu "Guidance & documents", by selecting the option "Reference documents". You can filter by the program (Horizon Europe, H2020) and by type of document (Work program, Grant Agreement, Proposal Templates, etc.). You have it prepared for all types of actions.

FIGURE 4.8.
Information and resources

Notifications and Updates: Users can subscribe to receive notifications and updates on funding opportunities, calls for proposals, events, and other relevant news related to EU funding programs.

5. GRANT AGREEMENT PREPARATION PROCEDURE

GAP session is the period from the positive evaluation of the project proposal, until the signature of the Grant Agreement. It includes several important steps:

28

- Administration of the online session at the Funding and Tenders portal
- Modification of the proposal according to evaluators comments
- Setting up and signature of the Consortium Agreement

TABLE 5.1.

The difference between Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement

GRANT AGREEMENT	CONSORTIUM ¹ AGREEMENT
- Signed between the EC and the beneficiaries; - Defines the rights and obligations of the beneficiaries towards the EC.	- Signed between the consortium members only; - Defines the rights and obligations between the beneficiaries (consortium members) themselves.

The session is much different in relation to the role of the PMO / PI (hereinafter: PI). If you are a partner, than you are following the guidelines of the coordinator and taking a portion of the assignments from the whole consortium. If you are a coordinator of the project, you are providing the guidelines, coordinate the preparation of the documents, draft the Consortium Agreement.

Once the project has been selected for funding, the coordinator takes over the communication and coordination of the steps named above. Within the institute, the researcher is responsible for communication within the consortium and with the PMO, who helps administratively. The details of such responsibilities is given below (**Table 5.2.**).

TABLE 5.2.

Roles of beneficiary as project partner

Task	PMO role	PI's role
Definition of the roles at the portal	Add the entire team at the Funding and Tenders portal	n/a
Signature of the Declaration on Honour	Prepare and sign the Declaration	n/a

¹ An example of updated DESCA Model Consortium Agreement for use in Horizon Europe projects. The revised model takes into account requirements stemming from the rules of the new EU Framework Programme Horizon Europe and experience of the user community in working with DESCA 2020, as well as other legal developments: 20221118_DESCA_HorizonEurope_Version_1.1_Word_final.docx (live.com)

Assignment of researchers to be involved in the implementation	Provides to the researcher a list of individuals from the portal for revision or confirmation. Once the list has been revised or confirmed, PMO make adequate action at the portal	The researcher propose revised list of names or confirms.
Preparation of the Description of Action (DoA) – Part B of the project	n/a	Make adequate changes according to the guidelines of the Coordinator
Comments on the Consortium Agreement	Coordinates the preparation of comments, proposed modifications of the Agreement. The Agreement is revised by the legal department of the Institute. PMO here only coordinates the document and feedback.	Coordinates the preparation of comments, proposed modifications of the Agreement. The Agreement is revised by the legal department of the Institute. PMO here only coordinates the document and feedback.
Signature of the Consortium Agreement	Coordinating the process of signature. PMO receives the instructions for signature (physical or digital signature) and logistic information (how many originals, ways of delivery – by post, scan by email – address) and triggers the internal approval and signature session. Once completed and signed Project office delivers the signed original(s) of the Agreement to the researcher and/or coordinator. PMO is also responsible, and in communication with the researcher, for receiving the fully signed version of the Consortium Agreement for the Institute archive.	Researcher is responsible for the delivery of the document to the PMO for the internal approval process.
Signature of the Grant Agreement	PMO organises and completes the Grant Agreement signature process	n/a

In case that you are the coordinator of the project selected for funding, you are first point of contact between the consortium, the Institute and the Project Officer, assigned by the EC, or its implementation agencies.

Same steps has to be taken, as presented in the beginning of the document, but in different role and with different effort. Also, the PMO takes control of certain tasks and responsibilities, in order to facilitate the process and increase the efficiency of the GAP session.

Before the launching the GAP phase within the consortium, preparation meeting between the researcher and the PMO is absolutely necessary in order to clearly divide the steps and procedures, as well as timing and milestones definition, so that everybody knows the to-do list and deadlines. These tasks will be evaluated and revised on regular internal meetings, where the GAP will be monitored and evaluated. Also, important step is to inform the Project Officer and introduce a member of the PMO who will also be in touch with him/her, so that the division of responsibilities are communicated with everyone. Also, researcher should inform the consortium and introduce a member of the PMO, who will take over the portion

of communication related to the administrative part of the GAP session and development of the Consortium Agreement.

Also, another important things is that there are two documents that are included in GAP procedure:

- Description of Action (DoA);
- Coordination document.

30

Revision of the first document DoA is in hands of the researcher, while the Coordination document is predominantly the responsibility of the PMO. DoA is only about the revision of the application according to the evaluator's comments, while the Coordination document is the tool for tracking the modifications required by the Project Officer.

The following steps and responsibilities apply for a beneficiary as a project coordinator (Table 5.3.).

TABLE 5.3.
Roles of beneficiary as project coordinator

Task	Project office role	PI's role
Definition of the roles at the portal	Add the entire team at the Funding and Tenders portal Communicate the procedure with partners and monitors its success	n/a
Signature of the Declaration on Honour	Prepare and sign the Declaration Communicate the procedure with partners and monitors its success	n/a
Assignment of researchers to be involved in the implementation	Provides to the researcher a list of individuals from the portal for revision or confirmation. Once the list has been revised or confirmed, PMO make adequate action at the portal Communicate the procedure with partners and monitors its success	The researcher propose revised list of names or confirms.
Modification of the Coordination document	Make necessary changes in the document Edit the history of changes Communicate it with the project officer	Provide inputs from the DoA to add into the Coordination document

Preparation of the Description of Action (DoA) – Part B of the project	Translate the editing of the DoA into the Coordination document	Make adequate changes according to the guidelines of the Coordinator Communicate the changes with the consortium and collect the inputs Revise and submit the DoA to the PMO, to communicate the revision together with the Coordination document
Drafting the Consortium Agreement	Coordinates the drafting of the Consortium Agreement (drafting will be done by the legal department) Collect the feedback from the partners Prepare the commented draft for legal department to make changes Prepare the final draft, according to the all agreed modifications	n/a
Signature of the Consortium Agreement	Communicates the final draft and collects signatures Distributes the fully signed Agreement to the partners	n/a
Signature of the Grant Agreement	Prepare and sign the Grant Agreement Communicate the procedure with partners and monitors its success	n/a

Once the GAP procedures are completed, you are ready to start your project!

6. GRANT AGREEMENT AND DESCRIPTION OF ACTION (DoA)

32

After the successful evaluation of proposal (your proposal has been selected for funding) the Project Coordinator will receive the **Evaluation Summary Report** and will be invited to prepare the **Grant Agreement**². The Grant Agreement is signed between the Coordinator and the European Commission and is deemed to enter into force on the day of the last signature. The Coordinator will have the task to transform the project proposal into a new document, called a **DoA**, which will become the technical annex (Annex 1)³ of the Grant Agreement and it outlines all the activities of the project as well as roles and responsibilities of every project partner. It is one among six Annexes of the Grant Agreement.⁴

6.1. Structure and content of the DoA

The structure and content of the DoA does not differ significantly from the proposal. It consists of two parts, which can be generated directly from the submitted proposal:

Part A provides administrative informations – in an online form. It contains the cover page, the project summary, the list of participants and the work plan tables (e.g. WP descriptions, deliverables, milestones). All the information for the part A needs to be entered ONLINE through the F&T Portal.

The budget table is also completed through online forms. It is included as a separate Annex 2 to the Grant Agreement.

Part B is the narrative part of the description of the action and it is crucial for a comprehensive understanding of the proposed project.

When preparing and submitting Part B, please adhere to the following instructions:

1. File Format and Submission:

Part B should be presented in a Word template.

Once completed, convert Part B to a PDF document for submission.

2. Origination from Proposal:

Initiate the creation of Part B by referencing the Part B section of your initial proposal submission. This ensures continuity and coherence in the narrative.

3. Structural Consistency:

Maintain the original structure and order of chapters and sections as outlined in the

²See Annotated Model Grant Agreement: [aga_en.pdf](#) (europa.eu)

³For a template see: [h2020-doa-ria-ia-csa_en.pdf](#) (europa.eu)

⁴The Grant Agreement is accompanied by 6 Annexes: Annex 1 - Description of Action (DoA), Annex 2 - Estimated budget of the action, Annex - Accession Forms, Annex 4 - Model for the financial statement, Annex 5 - Model for the certificate on the financial statements, and Annex

proposal guidelines. This consistency facilitates a seamless transition between the proposal and Part B.

4. Content: Introduction (a detailed introduction, including the background and context of the project), Objectives (clearly defined specific objectives the project aims to achieve), Methodology (methodologies and approaches planned for executing the project), Work Plan (a comprehensive work plan with timelines, milestones, and deliverables), Risk Assessment (identification of potential risks and outlines strategies for risk mitigation), Expected Results (anticipated outcomes and results of the project), Impact and Sustainability (the expected impact of the project and outlines sustainability measures).

5. Page Numbering:

All pages within the Part B document must be numbered for clarity and easy reference.

6. Footer Inclusion:

At the bottom of each page, include the following details:

Proposal number: Indicate the unique identifier assigned to your proposal.

Acronym: Incorporate the project acronym for quick identification.

»Part B«: Clearly state that the content belongs to Part B of the submission.

Part B should *NOT* contain any content that is already included in Part A.

GAP TASKS OF A PROJECT COORDINATOR:

- Complete the workplan tables in Part A (work package descriptions, deliverables and milestones)
- Double check the consistency of DoA and the proposal
- Check the PICs and other legal and administrative information
- Quality check if needed (results of ethics review, security scrutiny)

6.2. Can we change the DoA during project implementation?

While it's generally preferable to stick to the agreed-upon plan, modifications to the DoA may be necessary under certain circumstances. Here are common scenarios where modifying the DoA during project implementation could be considered:

- **Unforeseen Circumstances** (natural disasters, unforeseen regulatory changes, or unexpected events that significantly impact project implementation). Adjustments may be necessary to address challenges that were not foreseeable during the initial planning.
- **Evolving Project Needs** (new opportunities arise, or the project team identifies more effective ways to achieve objectives). Modifying the DoA allows the project to adapt to changing circumstances and optimize its approach for better outcomes
- **Resource Constraints** (budget adjustments, changes in available personnel, or unexpected resource limitations). Adapting the DoA ensures that the project remains feasible within the available resources.

- **Technological Advances** (introduction of new technologies that can enhance project efficiency or outcomes). Embracing technological advancements may require adjustments to the DoA to incorporate innovative solutions.
- **Stakeholder Input** (valuable insights from project stakeholders that suggest improvements or modifications to the original plan). Inclusion of stakeholder input can enhance the project's relevance and success.
- **Compliance Requirements** (changes in legal or regulatory requirements that necessitate adjustments to the project plan). Ensuring compliance with new regulations is critical, and modifications to the DoA may be necessary to meet updated standards.
- **Risk Mitigation** (proactive adjustments to mitigate identified risks and ensure the project's success). Modifying the DoA in response to potential risks helps enhance the project's resilience and adaptability.
- **Project Evaluation Findings** (feedback from interim project evaluations highlighting areas for improvement or adjustment). Incorporating lessons learned from evaluations can enhance the project's overall effectiveness.

When changing the DoA you may also consider the following:

Impact on Objectives: Changes to the DoA should not compromise the core objectives of the project. Before you make any changes, think about how they might affect your project's main goals. Make sure your adjustments don't impact the overall project goals.

Documentation: Thorough documentation of the proposed changes, the rationale behind them, and the subsequent approval process is critical. This documentation ensures accountability and provides a comprehensive record for both the beneficiary and the European Commission.

6.3. Amending grant agreement

A **grant agreement amendment** in Horizon Europe refers to a formal modification or alteration made to the terms and conditions of an existing grant agreement between the European Commission and a beneficiary (e.g., a research institution, university, company) that has been awarded funding for a project under the Horizon Europe program. Every grant agreement amendment as showed in **Table 6.1.** should be done before the end of the project. An amendment is necessary when one of the following changes occurs:

TABLE 6.1.
Grant agreement amendments

Amendment	Reason	Example
Change in Project Scope	If there are substantial modifications to the project objectives, activities, or outcomes.	Change to Annex 1, change in the title of the project or its acronym, starting date, duration or reporting periods or Resumption of project activities after a temporary suspension
Revisions to Project Timeline	If there are delays or accelerations in project milestones or completion dates.	Unforeseen circumstances, such as external events or changes in project priorities, impacting the project schedule.
Budget Modifications Beyond Allowed Flexibility	If proposed changes exceed the predefined limits of budget flexibility	Reallocation of funds that surpass the percentage allowed without prior approval.
Personnel Changes	If key project personnel listed in the original agreement change, and it's a requirement to notify or seek approval.	Principal Investigator or project coordinator changes during the course of the project.
Changes in Consortium or Partnerships	If there are alterations to the composition of the project consortium or collaborations with external partners.	Inclusion or exclusion of partner organizations, or changes in the roles and responsibilities of consortium members.
Ethical or Regulatory Considerations	If there are changes related to ethical considerations, regulatory approvals, or compliance requirements.	Modifications to the project that affect human subjects, animal welfare, or other ethical aspects.
Force Majeure Event	If unforeseen events, such as natural disasters or pandemics, significantly impact project implementation.	Delays or disruptions caused by events beyond the control of the grantee.
Intellectual Property or Publication Issues	If there are changes related to intellectual property rights (hereinafter PR) or restrictions on the dissemination of project results.	Adjustments to publication timelines or restrictions imposed by partner organizations.

**Notification for coordinators -
Not every change has to be subjected to amendment process!**

Grant agreement amendments are necessary when changes to the project are substantial or go beyond the allowed budget flexibility (see above). They formalize adjustments and ensure that all parties involved are aware of and agree to the modifications. In all other cases, especially to reduce administrative burdens, it is highly appreciated to use BUDGET FLEXIBILITY condition within which reallocation of funds within the approved budget without seeking prior approval from the funding agency is possible.

This flexibility allows for adjustments in resource allocation to respond to **changing circumstances** or **unforeseen challenges** during the project implementation.

The extent of budget flexibility varies among grant agreements. Some agreements may specify a percentage of the total budget that can be reallocated without approval, while others may require prior notification or approval for any budget modifications.

7. REPORTING UNDER HORIZON EUROPE

The precondition for reporting is the signature of the Grant Agreement by the Coordinator and the EU. Every project has a **project officer** from the EC or Respective Implementing Agency who works with the beneficiary or consortium to ensure the project is carried out as planned. The project officer is Coordinator's primary point of contact for any questions about grant agreement and reporting on the implementation of the project. By logging into your **Funding & Tenders Portal profile**, you can get in touch with your project officer.

Reporting responsibilities vary depending on the beneficiary's role in the project. The responsibilities of a project coordinator and project partner in terms of reporting under Horizon Europe are outlined in the structured comparison **Table 7.1.** below.

TABLE 7.1.
Reporting responsibilities based on beneficiary's role

TASK	PROJECT COORDINATOR	PROJECT PARTNER
Overall coordination	Coordinate all reporting activities throughout the project lifecycle. Ensure reporting deadlines are met and reports are submitted accurately.	Provide accurate and timely data and information to the project coordinator. Maintain records of project activities and outcomes.
Data collection and compilation	Gather necessary data and information from project partners. Review and consolidate inputs from all partners.	Provide inputs to the project coordinator for inclusion in reports. Document project activities, expenditures, and outcomes.

Quality assurance	Review and validate reports for accuracy and compliance. Address discrepancies and inconsistencies in reports.	Provide accurate and compliant financial records. Ensure ethical standards and regulatory obligations are met.
Communication and collaboration	Facilitate communication among project partners. Provide guidance and support to partners on reporting requirements.	Participate in dissemination activities and impact assessment. Maintain open communication with the coordinator.
Submission and follow-up	Submit reports within specified deadlines. Monitor acknowledgments and feedback from funding agencies.	Seek clarification or assistance from the coordinator as needed.
Risk management	Identify potential risks related to reporting. Develop mitigation strategies to address reporting risks.	n/a

Responsibilities described above also vary on types of action. Please note that the text in the table is focusing on the most frequently implemented types of action at National Institute of Chemistry, which include Research and Innovation Actions (RIA), Innovation Actions (IA), Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA), ERA-NET Actions and European Research Council (ERC) Actions.

There are different demands for mandatory reporting based on different types of action. They are further identified (**Table 7.2.**) and described below.

TABLE 7.2.
Mandatory reporting based on types of action

TYPE OF ACTION	MANDATORY REPORTS	MANDATORY ANNEXES
Research and Innovation Actions (RIA)	- Interim Progress Report (IPR) - Final Report - Financial Report	- Technical Report (Parts A & B) - Financial Annex
Innovation Actions (IA)	- Interim Progress Report (IPR) - Final Report - Financial Report	- Technical Report (Parts A & B) - Financial Annex
Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA)	- Deliverable Reports - Periodic Report - Final Report - Financial Report	- Training Annex - Career Development Plan (CDP)

ERA-NET Actions	- Interim Progress Report (IPR) - Final Report - Financial Report	- Financial Annex
European Research Council (ERC) Actions	- Deliverable Reports - Periodic Report - Final Report - Financial Report	- Scientific Annex - Financial Annex

38

Brief descriptions of mandatory Reports and Annexes

- Interim Progress Report (hereinafter IPR): An annual update on project progress, achievements, deviations, and risks. IPR must be submitted within 60 days after the end of each reporting period.
- Final Report: Summarizes the entire project, including outcomes, impacts, and future plans. Final Report must be submitted within 60 days after the end date of the project.
- Deliverable Reports: Documents specific outputs or milestones achieved during the reporting period. Deliverables Report must be submitted in accordance with the timing and conditions set out in the Grant agreement.
- Periodic Report: Provides an overview of project progress, including activities and implementation. Periodic report must be submitted within 60 days following the end of each reporting period.
- Training Annex: Details the training program, events, and opportunities provided to researchers.
- Career Development Plan (hereinafter CDP): Outlines career development opportunities for researchers participating in the project.
- Financial Report: Details project expenditures and financial status. Financial Report must be submitted within 60 days after the end date of the project.
- Technical Report (Part A & B): Part A provides a comprehensive overview of the project's scientific and technical aspects, including objectives, methodology, and expected outcomes. Part B contains detailed information on resources, management structure, and consortium members' roles and responsibilities.
- Financial Annex: Details project expenditures and supports the financial report.
- Scientific Annex: Provides detailed scientific information supporting the reports, such as research methodologies and findings.

The consortium or beneficiary shall submit reports in accordance with the timetable specified in the Grant Agreement in order to be eligible for payments. There are different types of reporting required based on the reporting content and timeline. They are further described in the **Table 7.3.** below

TABLE 7.3.**Types of reporting** (See chapters 10 and 11 for helpful guidelines and templates)

WHICH?	WHAT?	WHEN?
Continuous Reporting	Regular updates on the status of the project. Content: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • progress in achieving milestones • deliverables • updates to the publishable summary • response to critical risks, publications, communications activities, IPRs • programme-specific monitoring information (if required). 	from the beginning of a project (collaborative: all beneficiaries can edit)
Periodic Reporting	Periodic updates on the project progress in a specific period. It consists of the Technical Report and Financial Report. The Technical Report is itself also divided in two parts, Parts A and B: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Part A contains the structured tables with project information. • Part B (the narrative part) mirrors the application form and requires the participants to report on differences (delays, work not implemented, new subcontracts, budget overruns etc.). 	at the end of a reporting period (usually 60 days)
Final reporting	The report for the last reporting period, to close the grant. The system behaviour, screens and documents used are the same as for periodic reporting.	from the last reporting period on
Beneficiary termination reporting	In the event that a beneficiary must withdraw from the consortium, the coordinator is required to create a report in the Grant Management System detailing the payment distribution to the beneficiary as well as a technical report (part B and financial report).	as soon as the termination date is reached
Scientific Reporting	Description of beneficiary's contribution to the scientific part (summary for publication, deliverables, ethics, DMP, publications, patents, open data, major achievements and challenges, expeditions and awards, dissemination and outputs, keywords, problems and difficulties)	only for ERC grants

8. COMMUNICATION

Communicating about your project funded by the EC is a **legal obligation** because after receiving the EU grants (public funds) you are expected to actively engage in communication activities, to promote the projects and to publicly acknowledge the EU support.

40 As a project coordinator you will be faced with two types of communication: external and internal.

8.1 External communication

External communication involves engaging stakeholders, disseminating project outcomes, managing media relations, and ensuring compliance with regulations. By effectively communicating with the broader community, the project enhances visibility, explores collaboration opportunities, and contributes to its overall impact on research and innovation as well as to the success of the project. Therefore, all communications needs to be subjected to the **regulations and policies of Horizon Europe**, ensuring transparency and adherence to ethical standards. You can find all the explanations on Communication, Dissemination and Visibility in **the Article 17 of the AGA — Annotated Grant Agreement** document.⁶ As a beneficiary of the EU funding, you mustn't forget on the acknowledging of the following in your communication activities:

The EU flag (emblem) and funding statement⁵ (»Funded by the European Union« or »Co-funded by the European Union«) must be used in all communication and dissemination activities (incl. media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc), any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result results funded by the grant. It also needs to be easily visible for the public.

As all project – related communication and dissemination activities must convey accurate information, you need to include **the disclaimer**. It needs to be translated: *'Funded by the*

⁵ Article 17 – Communication, Dissemination and Visibility of the AGA for the EU funding programmes 2021-2027: [aga_en.pdf](#) (europa.eu).

⁶ Article 17.2 on Visibility of the AGA. : "Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate)."

European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

All the planned communication activities **MUST** be part of you **proposal** as a part of the **»IMPACT« section**. They can be incorporated either as a specific work package for communication or by including them in another work package where you can navigate among different typical communication activities (see Communication Network Indicators).

41

8.2 Internal communication

Internal communication aims to create a cohesive and informed project team, promoting collaboration, knowledge sharing, and efficient problem-solving.

Therefore, every project coordinator needs to keep the **address list** of members and other contact persons updated and available. He/she also initiates, prepares the meetings, proposes decisions and prepares the agenda of the meetings, chairs the meetings, prepares the minutes of the meetings and monitors the implementation of decisions taken at the meetings. Everyday work of a coordinator includes:

- establishing effective communication (tools⁷, channels),
- document the meeting minutes, action items, key decisions during each meeting, and setting the date for the next meeting,
- foster an open and collaborative communication culture,
- regularly reassess and adapt the communication strategies based on the evolving needs of the project,
- actively manage potential disputes among the project partners through acting according to CA, explaining the rules, options and mediation, and finding a compromise – safeguarding the interest of the project.

⁷ For example: mailing lists for the project and work package teams, regular Skype/Online or phone conference calls for smaller discussions, face-to-face meetings, common platform, etc.

TABLE 8.1.

Beneficiary's roles based on type of communication

COMMUNICATION	TYPE	ROLES OF PROJECT COORDINATOR	ROLES OF PROJECT PARTNER
<p>Communication with the EC</p>	<p>Regular Updates</p>	<p>Provide regular updates to the EC on project progress, achievements, and any challenges faced.</p> <p>Be transparent about project developments and communicate proactively.</p>	<p>Keep partners informed about EC communication and reporting requirements.</p> <p>Collaborate with partners to provide accurate and timely data for reporting.</p> <p>Share relevant EC guidelines and updates with the consortium.</p> <p>Encourage partners to communicate any potential issues that may impact the project's relationship with the EC.</p>
	<p>Compliance and Reporting</p>	<p>Ensure compliance with reporting requirements specified in the grant agreement.</p> <p>Submit timely and accurate reports, addressing any queries or concerns raised by the EC.</p>	
	<p>Coordination Meetings</p>	<p>Schedule periodic coordination meetings with EC representatives to discuss project status, potential issues, and upcoming milestones.</p>	
	<p>Proactive Issue Resolution</p>	<p>Communicate promptly if there are any anticipated issues or deviations from the project plan.</p> <p>Propose solutions and mitigation strategies for any challenges.</p>	
	<p>EC Guidelines Adherence</p>	<p>Stay informed about EC guidelines and policies relevant to your project.</p> <p>Align project activities with the overarching goals and requirements of Horizon Europe.</p>	

COMMUNICATION	TYPE	ROLES OF PROJECT COORDINATOR	ROLES OF PROJECT PARTNER
Internal communication with the partners	Regular Partner Updates	<p>Establish a clear communication plan for regular updates among project partners.</p> <p>Share progress reports, achievements, and important announcements.</p>	<p>Actively participate in consortium meetings and provide updates on individual tasks.</p> <p>Utilize collaborative platforms for efficient communication and document sharing.</p> <p>Communicate any challenges or issues that may impact the project.</p> <p>Adhere to the communication plan and timelines set by the Project Coordinator.</p>
	Collaborative Platforms	<p>Utilize collaborative online platforms for internal communication, document sharing, and collaboration.</p> <p>Ensure all partners have access to necessary project-related information.</p>	
	Task Assignments and Responsibilities	<p>Clearly define and communicate task assignments and responsibilities to each partner.</p> <p>Foster a collaborative environment by encouraging active participation.</p>	
	Periodic Consortium Meetings	<p>Schedule periodic consortium meetings to discuss overall project progress, challenges, and upcoming activities.</p> <p>Use these meetings to share insights and lessons learned among partners.</p>	
	Work Package Meetings	<p>Organize focused work package meetings to address specific aspects of the project.</p> <p>Encourage collaboration and information exchange within smaller groups.</p>	

COMMUNICATION	TYPE	ROLES OF PROJECT COORDINATOR	ROLES OF PROJECT PARTNER
Meetings	Regular Progress Meetings	<p>Schedule regular progress meetings to review project milestones, timelines, and achievements.</p> <p>Use these meetings to identify and address any roadblocks or challenges</p>	<p>Actively participate in all types of meetings organized by the Project Coordinator.</p> <p>Contribute insights, feedback, and updates during progress and evaluation meetings.</p> <p>Attend dissemination and exploitation meetings to align strategies and goals.</p> <p>Ensure representation in steering committee meetings, providing relevant input.</p>
	Kick-off Meeting	Conduct a comprehensive kick-off meeting at the project's commencement to align all partners, discuss project goals, and clarify roles	
	Review and Evaluation Meetings	<p>Organize periodic review and evaluation meetings to assess the effectiveness of project activities and outcomes.</p> <p>Use feedback to improve project implementation.</p>	
	Steering Committee Meetings	Establish a steering committee and organize periodic meetings to provide strategic guidance and decision-making.	
	Dissemination and Exploitation Meetings	Schedule meetings specifically focused on dissemination and exploitation strategies to ensure effective communication of project results.	
	Regular technical meetings	<p>These meetings focus on technical aspects, such as discussing implementation details, troubleshooting, and ensuring alignment with project requirements.</p> <p>These meetings facilitate knowledge exchange, problem-solving, and decision-making related to the project's technical components.</p>	
	Final meeting	Is organized at the closing up the project, focusing on project closure and continuation of collaboration. Communicating with the partners – proper farewell. Distributing the final payment. Submitting the report on the distribution of EU contribution. Final administrative steps, informing all partners about their final duties. Making sure that all public results are available, Website maintenance is ensured for 5 extra years. All is archived, administered.	

9. DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION

In accordance with the Article 17 on Communication, Dissemination and Visibility of the AGA:

“Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in accordance with Annex 1 and in a strategic, coherent and effective manner. Before engaging in a communication or dissemination activity expected to have a major media impact, the beneficiaries must inform the granting authority».

45

dissemination and exploitation activities are also obligatory⁸ in order to enhance the visibility of the work and results, to help diffuse knowledge, increase the use of Research & Innovation (R&I) projects results in the EU and beyond and support a more robust evidence-based policy making.

What it needs to be highlighted here is another aspect of dissemination and exploitation activities – namely, **Intellectual Property Rights (hereinafter: IPR)**. According to the Article 16⁹ of the AGA document, as a beneficiary you must provide access to essential pre-existing information, ensuring compliance with third-party rights. Notably, the granting authority does not acquire ownership of project results, maintaining the tangible or intangible effects and associated intellectual property rights with the beneficiaries.

As a project coordinator, when dealing with the IPR you should pay special attention to the following:

- You should develop a robust exploitation strategy outlining how the project's intellectual property will be utilized and commercialized. This includes considerations for licensing, partnerships, or any other means of leveraging project results.
- You should align dissemination plans with the identified intellectual property. Clearly communicate any restrictions on the use or reproduction of project results in dissemination activities.

Further, dissemination refers to the active and planned communication of project results and findings to a **wide range of audiences** beyond the project consortium. In this way, project can benefit a larger group of persons and reach wider target groups. Dissemination is a critical aspect of research and innovation projects, and it aims to maximize the impact of the project outcomes by sharing knowledge, expertise, and tangible results with various **stakeholders (Table 9.1.)**.

⁸ Regulation (EU) 2021/695 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013 (OJ 12.5.2021 L 170/1).

⁹ See Article 16 on IPR of the AGA document [aga_en.pdf](#) (europa.eu).

TABLE 9.1.
Dissemination tools based on stakeholders

RELEVANT STAKEHOLDERS	DISSEMINATION TOOLS
Scientific Community	Sharing research findings, methodologies, and scientific insights with the broader scientific community. This may involve publishing research papers, articles, and participating in conferences. Virtual and in-person workshops for knowledge exchange; Webinars featuring guest speakers from the project team.
Industry and Business	Communicating project outcomes that have potential applications or benefits for industries and businesses. This can support technology transfer, innovation, and the development of new products or services. Collaborative forums and innovation workshops; Industry-focused webinars with Q&A sessions.
Policy-makers and Government bodies	Providing relevant project results to inform policy-making and decision-making processes. This ensures that the outcomes of research contribute to the development of effective policies and strategies. Policy roundtables and targeted briefings; Engaging in consultations and feedback sessions.
General public	Disseminating information in a more accessible and understandable format for the general public. This may include outreach activities, educational programs, and initiatives to increase public awareness and understanding. Science cafés and public talks; Educational outreach programs in collaboration with schools.
Other research projects	Sharing lessons learned, best practices, and methodologies with other research projects. This contributes to the collective knowledge within the research community and promotes collaboration.
Other engagement activities	Regular updates on project website and social media, scientific publications at key milestones, industry-focused workshops and webinars, initial policy briefs and engagement with relevant stakeholders. final project conference or symposium, comprehensive project report and open-access publications.

As a project coordinator you need to co-create **a well-defined dissemination strategy** with your Communication and Dissemination manager. This strategy should include the following elements:

- Set the **objectives** related to maximize research impact (share research findings, methodologies, and innovations to contribute to the broader scientific community and advance knowledge in the field), promotion of industrial uptake (communicate project outcomes with industries and businesses to encourage technology transfer, innovation, and potential applications in the marketplace), informing policy-making process (provide relevant project results to inform policy-makers and government bodies, influencing evidence-based policy development), and enhancing public understanding (disseminate information in accessible formats to increase public awareness and understanding of the project's goals, achievements, and societal impact).

- Clearly identify your **target audiences that will benefit from the project results** (scientific community, industry and businesses, policy-makers and government bodies, general public) and determine the most effective **communication channels** and tools for disseminating information, such as publications, websites, social media, workshops, and conferences.
- Plan the timing of dissemination activities – set the **timeline and milestones** for reaching specific audience at different stages of the project.
- Ensure that all the publications and data will be made openly accessible (see Horizon Europe Programme Guide).
- Regularly assess the effectiveness of dissemination activities through feedback, analytics, and stakeholder engagement.

47

On the other hand, **an exploitation strategy** should focus on:

- **Identification of Exploitable Results:** Identify project results with potential for further development, commercialization, or application beyond the project's lifespan.
- **Market Analysis:** Conduct a market analysis to understand the potential demand, competition, and opportunities for exploiting specific project outcomes.
- **Intellectual Property (IP) Protection:** Determine whether any project results require intellectual property protection (patents, copyrights) to safeguard potential exploitation.
- **Collaboration and Partnerships:** Explore collaborations and partnerships with industry, businesses, or other research organizations to facilitate the exploitation of project results.
- **Technology Transfer:** If applicable, outline strategies for transferring technology or knowledge from the project to external entities for practical applications.
- **Commercialization Plans:** Develop plans for commercializing applicable project outcomes, including licensing agreements, spin-off companies, or other commercial ventures.
- **Regulatory Compliance:** Ensure that the exploitation plan considers and complies with relevant regulatory requirements and standards.
- **Long-Term Sustainability:** Assess the long-term sustainability of exploited results, considering factors such as market trends, evolving technologies, and potential societal impact.

A communication, dissemination and exploitation (hereinafter: CDE) plan should be an integral part of the following stages of the project, as shown in the Table 9.2. **Within 6 months after the date of signature of GA**, a plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results including communication activities needs to be provided by the beneficiaries and it needs to be regularly updated. normally with the first six months of the action and regularly updated.

TABLE 9.2.**Use of CDE Plan in different stages of the project**

48

STAGE	ACTIVITY
Proposal stage	Even before the project begins, during the proposal stage, applicants are required to outline an initial plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results. This plan is submitted as part of the proposal and is evaluated by the EC as a criterion for funding.
Project Kick-off	Once the project is awarded, the detailed plan for exploitation and dissemination is developed during the initial project kick-off phase. This plan should be an integral part of the overall project management plan.
Early Project Phases	As the project progresses through its initial phases, the plan should be redefined based on more detailed information about the project's goals, outcomes, and stakeholders. Early engagement with partners is crucial to align strategies.
Exploitation Strategy	The exploitation part of the plan outlines how the project results will be used beyond the project's duration. This includes identifying potentially exploitable outcomes such as patents, new technologies, or commercial applications.
Dissemination Strategy	The dissemination aspect focuses on communication activities to share project results widely. This involves defining target audiences, communication channels, and a timeline for sharing information throughout the project.
Regular Review and Updates	The plan for exploitation and dissemination should be regularly reviewed and updated to reflect changes in project goals, outcomes, and stakeholder engagement.
Mid-Term Review	Around the mid-term of the project, a review of the plan should take place. Any necessary adjustments can be made based on lessons learned, changes in project direction, or emerging opportunities.
Final Project Stages	As the project nears completion, the plan is finalized, and the implementation of the dissemination and exploitation activities is carried out. This includes organizing final conferences, submitting publications, and implementing the exploitation strategy.
Post-Project	After the project ends, ongoing efforts may be needed to continue the exploitation of results. This may involve technology transfer, commercialization, or further collaboration with stakeholders.
Reporting to the EC	The EC often requires project coordinators to provide regular reports on dissemination and exploitation activities as part of project reporting obligations.

10. HELPFUL GUIDELINES

- EU Funding & Tenders Online Manual
- National Contact Points for Horizon Europe
- Horizon Europe Programme Guide
- EU Grants Amendment Guide

49

FIGURE 10.1.
EU Funding and Tenders Online Manual

FIGURE 10.2.
National Contact points for Horizon Europe

FIGURE 10.3.
Horizon Europe Programme Guide

FIGURE 10.4.
EU Grants Ammendment Guide

FIGURE 10.5.
Common mistakes to avoid

FIGURE 10.6.
CORDIS - database of projects supported by HE

FIGURE 10.7.
EU guidelines on the responsible use of generative AI in research

FIGURE 10.8.
European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity

FIGURE 10.9.
European Commission's Research and Innovation Portal

FIGURE 10.10.
European IP Helpdesk

FIGURE 10.11.
Gender in EU research

FIGURE 10.12.
Horizon Results Booster

FIGURE 10.13.
Horizon Europe Results Platform

FIGURE 10.14.
Partnering opportunities – Enterprise Europe Network

FIGURE 10.15.
Partnering opportunities – Funding and Tenders Portal

11. TEMPLATES

FIGURE 11.1.
Minutes of the meeting

FIGURE 11.2.
Periodic report

FIGURE 11.3.
Horizon Europe Reference documents

CIP - Kataložni zapis o publikaciji

Narodna in univerzitetna knjižnica, Ljubljana

005.8:001.891:061.1EU(035)

336.531.2:001.891(4)(035)

PROJECT Management in EU Grant Funding : handbook : National Institute of Chemistry / [authors Barbara Tišler ... [et al.] ; editor Nastja Vodeb]. - Ljubljana : National Institute of Chemistry, 2024

ISBN 978-961-6104-91-3

COBISS.SI-ID 189933315

REPUBLIKA SLOVENIJA
MINISTRSTVO ZA VISOKO ŠOLSTVO,
ZNANOST IN INOVACIJE

Financira
Evropska unija
NextGenerationEU

Projekt sofinancirata Republika Slovenija, Ministrstvo za visoko šolstvo, znanost in inovacije ter Evropska unija – NextGenerationEU